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Preparing for
an Elder Friendly Hong Kong
共創長者更美好明天

賽馬會長者計劃新里程
A Jockey Club Initiative for Seniors

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Chapter 1

Understanding the Ageing
Experience:
A Life Story Perspective

DISCUSSANT 2

From Medical History Taking to Story Listening

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The ancient roots for “disease” in English and “病” in Chinese both signify “being unwell” as told from the patient’s story: the English origin of “disease” was “dis-ease”,¹ while “𠄎”, the Chinese root of “病”, symbolized a sick person resting in bed in a propped up position.²

Advances in medicine in elucidating the aetiologies of “dis-ease,” often to microscopic and molecular levels, led to the emergence of objective, scientific concept of “disease” from earlier subjective ideas of “dis-ease,” so much so that nowadays more emphasis is being put on structured medical history taking to detect a particular disease pattern rather than listening to the patient’s story of “dis-ease.” Thus, the sick man “disappeared” in the modern society as “doctors directed their gaze not on the individual sick person but on the disease of which his or her body was the bearer.”³

In medical history taking, a patient may be viewed as a set of symptoms instead of a person. When an elderly patient dwells on her discomfort or dis-ease without fitting into the patterns of diseases described in medical texts, a doctor may label the patient as a “poor historian.” “Geriatric patients are sometimes described as ‘poor historians’ because they do not ‘give a good history’. But an historian is a person who writes history, not one who provides the facts. Taking the history is the real intellectual challenge of medicine. The “good historian” is the good physician. Patients are never “bad historians”; doctors sometimes are.”⁴

If “dis-ease” is not recognized, a diagnostic pathway won’t occur, and an elder might be labeled as “social problem,” and the solution thought to be social or institutional care. The dichotomous view of an elder with “dis-ease” as either “medical” or “social” would not fit into her fragile ecosystem of diseases, drugs and adverse social factors with complex interactions. In the words of Bernard Isaacs, “Elderly patients are admitted to hospital not

because of social problems, but because of medical problems with social consequences, or social problems with medical consequences.”⁴

Comprehensive geriatric assessment is a process of knowing the elderly person: recognizing “dis-ease”; detecting causative diseases and environmental factors (drugs, social); matching “dis-ease” to diseases; in order that “dis-ease” can be reversed or reduced through appropriate interventions, thus protecting a frail elder from functional decline and premature institutional placement.

In narrative-based medicine, the aim is to ensure that the life-world voice of a patient is listened to and heard, rather than being drowned out by the scientific-technocratic voice of medicine.⁵ With narrative gerontology, the elderly person can be cared for and understood in the broader perspective of his background, beliefs and values, fears and concerns, and preferences and wishes. For example, a hospitalized 78-year-old man was reported to be “poorly motivated” to undergo rehabilitation. On further questioning and listening, he unravelled a story of fear of further falls after a fall while bathing, as well as depression from loss of function and a sense of being burden to his family members; all these stood in sharp contrast to the splendid photographic scenes he captured few months prior to hospitalization. Further investigation revealed drug-induced unsteadiness as a cause of his falls. His balance and mobility improved upon reducing the offending drug and subsequent rehabilitation. His morale and self-esteem were boosted by listening, encouragement, and involving him in artwork creation.⁶

To tune in with the Cadenza symposium’s theme of “advent of an elder friendly Hong Kong,” adopting a life-story perspective can help in the provision of coordinated services to elders through collaboration and listening to an elder by asking the right question “*who* is this elder?” (listening to his/her story so as to provide person-centred care), instead of just focusing on “*where* should he/she be placed?” (a decision that is often resource-driven). In the words of Stephen Watkins, “The purpose of community care is to promote privacy, dignity and independence and provide resources for living. It is a philosophy, not a place.”⁷

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